

VINTAGE INSCRIPTIONS SIMILARITY

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Abstract

The article deals with the connection between the Old Turkic inscriptions and the Scandinavian runes. The ancient Turkic inscription found in Orkhon Yenisei in 17-18 centuries caused European scientists to admire. It is known that western scholars have come to the conclusion that the Turkic inscriptions originates from Europe by studying the secrets of Hunnus inscriptions. However, this is the main root of this article, which seeks to reconcile this viewpoint with denial. The article attempts to clarify the fact that the Great Turkish Empire can bring its culture and civilization to the conquest of Western European countries.

Ancient Turkic inscription with 2500-year history from the beginning of the 5- 4th century A.D., it has been proven that archaeologists have come to prove that Scandinavian Rune has reached the Turkic steppe. During the research works by scientists such as S. Sydykov, K. Konkobaev, S.Karzhaubai, ASAmanzholov, A.Bakhti, T. Barfield, A.N. Bernstein, and E.Tompson were used.

Every nation in the world has its genealogy, peculiarities, and viewpoints. Each nation has its own language, customs, thinking system and value. It is common today that the ancient Turkic language, which has been around for 300 years, has a great deal of social studies.

The main point of this paper is that the history of ancient Turkic inscriptions was formed 4-5 centuries before the Scandinavian Rune inscription, and that this subject should still be studied in depth. The article focuses on scientific research from current scientists.

Keywords: Old Turkic Inscription, Runic Inscriptions, Scandinavian Runes.

There are quite a few opinions about the origin of the ancient Turkish script. To date, it has been almost 300 years since the discovery of the first ancient Turkish inscription. European scientists who were the first to study suggested that this writing could come from Europe. However, at the moment these opinions are said to be erroneous. Therefore, new research is still needed on this topic. In the article we are writing today, we are looking to prove that the opinions of former European scientists about the fact that runic writing came to the Turkish steppes from the West are erroneous. Here are some historical facts and arguments that testify to our opinion. We cannot say that this article is exactly the first study on this topic. In this regard, the results of the study were presented.

Zachariah Ritordun, who wrote the Syrian Chronicle about the ancient Turkic writing in the middle of the second century, brings our opinion closer to the truth that the Huns wrote more than a thousand years ago. This is due to the fact that the "Hun inscription" Here must

also be this ancient Turkish inscription. In 568, the Turks brought a letter from the Khan to Constantinople. This letter is referred to in the sources as the Scythian inscription. This information was provided by A. N. Kononov quotes in his book "Grammar of the language of the Turkic runic monuments (II-IX) "and notes that the opinion is taken from the work of N. V. Pigulevskaya" Siberian east stories of the people of the USSR " [1.9].

Since the III century BC, when the ancient Turkic script began to be used, natural stone (rock), stone (slab stone, specially processed for carving text), animal skins, felt, wood, paper, gold, silver were used. ...drawings on the stone surface date back to the Scythian (belly Oguz), saka, Hunnu, Turkic times. More precisely, it has a 2000-year history from the tenth century BC to the tenth century BC. [2, 40]

The inscription on a ceramic pot found in Fergana and the city where sheep were killed dates back to the II-III centuries BC [3, 8]. A. S. Amanzholov, A. Bakhti speak in their works about some similarities between the ancient Turkish script and the Sumerian script, which has been in use since the tenth century BC.

To prove that the Sumerians, who were engaged in nomadic cattle breeding, were Asians, and their language did not belong to the Semitic or Hindu groups, A. Bakhti pebel, S. N. Kramer, K. V. Keram, E. Ceren cite their research as an argument. The Sumerian-Kazakh proximity, connection is evidenced by the fact that the sound and meaning of 46 words are the same or close, some of the same characters are found, in addition, various similarities in traditions and Customs [4].

Each people in the world has its own origin, identity and its own worldview. Each nation has its own language, its own customs, its own system of thinking, its own values. If we say that each spring has a source of origin, then it is quite possible that all languages have only one language. We can see from the information about the tower of Babel, which is found in the Bible, that there was only one language in the whole world. Whether or not to recognize the Bible scientifically is another matter, and we must take into account that it is one of the oldest sources written in the Middle East. According to this legend, The Roots of the entire language were the basis of the language, culture, customs, writing of the people that existed between the Tigris and Euphrates, the language, culture, customs, writing of this people, not only the ancient Turks, but also the language, culture, customs, writing of all nationalities and nationalities in the modern world. It is quite possible that there is a connection between the Turkish script and the Sumerian script.

Some works have been made to find out where the ancient ancient Turkish script came from, and now we will try to find an answer to the question of what inscriptions can appear on the basis of Turkish script.

The secret "rune" inscriptions along the Yenisei aroused the interest of European scientists in the XVIII-XVIII centuries due to the fact that they were very similar in appearance to the Scandinavian script. He tried to prove that the ancestor of Europeans (Finno-Ugric) was Altai [2, 11]. The number of such records increased, and only in the nineteenth century it was discovered that the language of these records was Turkish, and the pronunciation of all characters was distinguished [3,7]. After learning that these inscriptions were written in Turkish, European scientists continued to prove that their ancestor was Altai? What kind of Europeans are we talking about?

The Great Migration of the Huns, which shook Eurasia, brought unprecedented changes to Europe. Moving from East to West, the people continued to occupy new lands without

haste. In 375, the Huns crossed the Volga River and in a few years captured the entire Black Sea territory. The local population-the goth tribes-became part of the Huns.

In 395, the capital of the Eastern Roman Empire arrived in Constantinople. The Eastern Roman emperor was obliged to pay tribute to the Huns in gold. Destroyed the Burgundian Kingdom on the territory of modern France.

The invasion of Europe by the Huns – the "land of horsemen" and the Alans, who destroyed the Ostrogoths state between the Baltic Sea and the Black Sea, initiated the Great Migration of peoples.

The settlement of the lower Franks in the modern Netherlands, which belonged to Rome in 400.

402 years. The first attack of Alarich, King of the Visigoths, on Italy, which was defeated by the Roman army.

In 406, the Franks, displaced by vandals, alemans, and Alans from the Rhine, crossed the Left Bank of the Rhine. The Alans settled on the right bank.

409 years. The entry of vandals and Alans into Spain.

410 years. The invasion and plunder of Rome by the Visigoths under the leadership of Alarich.

In 415, the Alans, who conquered Spain in 409, and the vandals were ousted by the Visigoths.

In 434, all the power of the Huns passes to Attila.

In 449, Britain is occupied by the Anglos, Saxons and yuts.

450 years. The movement of the Huns, Gepids, Avars, Bulgars, Pechenegs and kumans through modern Romania.

In 451, the Romans United with the Visigoths under the leadership of Flavia Aeeas, pushing Attila beyond the Rhine.

In 452, the Huns devastated northern Italy. Pope Leo the great with the power of the word saves Rome from complete collapse.

In 570, Asian nomadic Avar tribes formed states on the border of modern Hungary and Lower Austria [5; 6; 7; 8; 9].

Perhaps one of the Huns who influenced such changes throughout Europe did not remain and moved back to Asia. Then it is impossible to deny that among modern Europeans there are many descendants of the same Huns. The inscription of the same Huns, which we noted above, with a history of 2000 years, also went with them to Europe. More than 6,000 artifacts with runic inscriptions have been found in Europe. At the moment, its number is increasing. Most of them are in Sweden, Norway (1600), Denmark (800). The geographical area of the rune inscriptions covers a very wide range from Greenland to Constantinople. This writing, which was used in some areas of Sweden from the first centuries of our census until the nineteenth century, is divided into the common Germanic high runes and the lower runes used by some Germanic tribes.

About 200 monuments have been found in Norway, inscribed in the upper rune, and in addition to weapons from the European island of Gotland, Prussia, Poland and Ukraine,

amulets, necklaces, tools have been carved on stones in Scandinavia since the fifth century. On coins dating from the period 450-550 BC, found in Denmark, inscriptions with symbols belonging to this upper rune are found. This time coincides with the period of migration of the Huns to Europe.

The upper rune is an archaic system of writing. This is due to the peculiarities of the paleography and writing language of the upper rune script. One characteristic characteristic of early European writing is the absence of a clear writing direction, that is, writing is written from right to left, and vice versa from left to right. Over time, writing from left to right becomes a priority. It is interesting that in one monument there is also a parallel writing of the inscription in both directions. In the same monuments, the text was not separated at all, in the same texts, sentences were separated by a colon. For a long time it was believed that the language of writing was ataskandinavian, due to the fact that most of the upper rune inscriptions were found in the Scandinavian territory, especially in Denmark. But at the moment this opinion is refuted.

It is proved that the language of the monuments written in the upper rune does not belong to a single ancient Germanic dialect. The upper rune has been in use for more than 6 centuries, covering a large area, and the fact that the language and stylistic features of these inscriptions remained unchanged until the VII century attracted the attention of runologists [10]. It is possible that this inscription, the language of which does not belong to any of the dialects of the ancient Germanic tribes, was widely used in Europe during the period when the direct Huns shook all of Europe. Otherwise, the Scandinavian writing "rune" would not be a "secret" writing for them. And the meeting of the words of the ancient Turkic language in any Turkic peoples clarifies that the opinion of our scientists is not unfounded.

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